

A NEW LOOK AT THIN-WALLED COMPOSITE BEAM MODELING APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

A review of thin-walled composite beam theories show significant differences in the derived expressions for the stiffness coefficients. A variationally asymptotical analysis of two dimensional shell theory is developed in order to isolate the effects contributing to these differences. The displacement field and associated stiffness coefficients are derived. The analysis is based on the minimization of the shell energy. The differences among the various theories predictions are found to be the result of the out-of-plane warping contribution to the displacement field. An illustration of the predictions from various theories is provided for two composite beam configurations.

INTRODUCTION

Several theories have been developed for the analysis of thin-walled anisotropic beams. However, there are significant differences in the derived expressions for the stiffness coefficients. An extensive review is provided in Ref. [1].

A basic element in the analytical modeling development is the derivation of the effective stiffness coefficients and governing equations which allows the three-dimensional ($3D$) state of stress to be recovered from a one-dimensional ($1D$) beam formulation. For isotropic or orthotropic materials this is a classical problem, which is considered in a number of text books such as Refs. [2]-[9]. For generally anisotropic materials, a number of $1D$ theories have been developed in Refs. [10]-[16].

Missing from the review of Ref. [1] and all other current publications is the work of Reissner and Tsai [10]. It presents an exact solution to the governing equilibrium, compatibility and constitutive relationships of shell theory. Closed as well as open cross-sections were considered. However, the authors did not provide an explicit form for the displacement field and left to the reader the derivation of the expressions for the stiffness coefficients. Also a number of assumptions were adopted in the development such as neglecting the coupling between in-plane strains and curvature which can be significant in anisotropic materials. An investigation of the influence of these assumptions on the predictions is needed in order to assess the accuracy of the theory.

Mansfield and Sobey [11] and Libove [12] obtained the beam flexibilities relating the stretching, twisting and bending deformations to the applied axial load, torsional and bending moments for a special origin and axes orientation. They adopted the assumptions of a negligible hoop stress resultant and a membrane state in the thin-walled beam section. Although they did not refer to the work of Reissner and Tsai [10], surprisingly when their theories are applied to the special case where the classical assumptions of neglecting shear and hoop stress and constant

Figure 1: Coordinate Systems.

shear flow are adopted, their stiffnesses coincide. However, one has to carry out details to show this result.

A pertinent element in the analytical modeling development is the inclusion of section warping. The major difference among the various theories lies in the methodology used to eliminate warping and consequently obtain a 1D theory. The work of Refs. [13]-[19] use the displacement field of thin-walled isotropic beams with shear deformation as the basis of their analytical development. In Refs. [14] and [16] the torsional rigidity is derived in terms of Classical Lamination Theory in what the author described as a “practical manner”. In Refs. [15] and [18] a shear correction factor has been introduced in order to reduce the overestimated bending stiffness. This factor was derived for the case of pure torsion by using the virtual work method and enforcing compatibility. While this approach shows an improvement in predictions, it is problem dependent. Another modification was proposed in the finite element formulation of Ref. [20]. This formulation aims at minimizing the error associated with the neglect of bending-related warping in the theory of Ref. [13]. This modification was based on shear stiffness correction factors determined by numerical comparison of results with an MSC/NASTRAN solution of cantilevered beam configurations loaded transversely at the free end.

The contribution of out-of-plane warping was considered recently by Kosmatka [21]. Local in-plane deformations and out-of-plane warping of the cross-section were expressed in terms of unknown functions. These functions were assumed to be proportional to the axial strain, bending curvature and twist rate within the cross-section and were determined using a finite element modeling.

This summary points to the necessity of addressing two fundamental issues. The first, is the effect of the material’s anisotropy on the displacement field and how to include its contribution in a consistent manner. No rigorous proof is provided to validate the assumed displacement fields in Refs. [13]-[19] for beams made of anisotropic material as indicated by the various correction factors introduced. The second, is whether the cross sectional warping is restricted to torsional behavior as is the case for isotropic materials. The present work addresses these issues by using an asymptotical analysis of 2D shell energy to derive the 1D displacement field. As a consequence, the material’s anisotropy is accounted for in a consistent manner and the deformation modes that have a lead contribution in the energy emerge naturally.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE ANALYTICAL MODEL

Coordinate Systems

Consider the slender thin-walled elastic cylindrical shell shown in Fig. 1. The length of the shell is denoted by L , its thickness by h , the radius of curvature of the middle surface by R and the maximum cross sectional dimension by d . It is assumed that

$$d \ll L \quad h \ll d \quad h \ll R \quad (1)$$

It is convenient to consider simultaneously two coordinate systems for the description of the state of stress in thin-walled beams. The first one is the cartesian system x, y and z . The axial

coordinate is x while y and z are associated with the beam cross section. The second coordinate system, is the curvilinear system x, s and ξ . The circumferential coordinate s is measured along the tangent to the middle surface in a counter-clockwise direction whereas ξ is measured along the normal to the middle surface. The coordinate ξ lies within the limits

$$-\frac{h(s)}{2} \leq \xi \leq \frac{h(s)}{2}$$

The shell thickness varies along the circumferential direction and is denoted by $h(s)$. Equations $y = y(s)$ and $z = z(s)$ define the closed contour Γ in the y, z plane.

Displacement Field

The displacement field in the cartesian coordinate system may be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 &= U_1(x) + \tilde{u}_1(s, x) \\ v_2 &= U_2(x) \frac{dy}{ds} + U_3(x) \frac{dz}{ds} + \varphi(x) r_n \\ v &= U_2(x) \frac{dz}{ds} - U_3(x) \frac{dy}{ds} - \varphi(x) r_t \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $U_1(x)$, $U_2(x)$ and $U_3(x)$ represent the rigid body translations along the x , y and z coordinates while $\varphi(x)$ is the rigid body rotation or angle of twist. The projection vector of any point on the center line of the cross section in the normal and tangential direction is denoted by r_n and r_t , respectively. The unknown function $\tilde{u}_1(s, x)$ is determined from energy consideration.

The energy of the shell Φ per unit middle surface area is

$$2\Phi = A_{11} (\gamma_{11})^2 + A_{22} (\gamma_{22})^2 + 4A_{66} (\gamma_{12})^2 + 2A_{12}\gamma_{11}\gamma_{22} + 4A_{16}\gamma_{11}\gamma_{12} + 4A_{26}\gamma_{22}\gamma_{12} \quad (3)$$

where the A_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, 6$) are the laminate axial stiffnesses [22] and $\gamma_{\alpha\beta}$ ($\alpha, \beta = 1, 2$) the in-plane strain components. In Eq. (3) the energy associated with membrane behavior is considered only since its contribution is much larger than the bending energy [23]. The energy of the shell can be written as

$$I = \int_S \Phi dS \quad (4)$$

where dS is the area of a middle surface element. For the case of no internal pressure acting on the shell, the hoop stress resultant is negligibly small and may be ignored [23], thus

$$N_{22} = \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \gamma_{22}} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Combine Eq. (5) with Eq. (3) to obtain

$$\gamma_{22} = -\frac{1}{A_{22}} (A_{12}\gamma_{11} + 2A_{26}\gamma_{12}) \quad (6)$$

The energy density takes the form

$$2\Phi_1 = \min_{\gamma_{22}} 2\Phi = A(s) (\gamma_{11})^2 + 2B(s) \gamma_{11} \gamma_{12} + C(s) (\gamma_{12})^2 \quad (7)$$

where

$$A(s) = A_{11} - \frac{(A_{12})^2}{A_{22}} \quad B(s) = 2 \left[A_{16} - \frac{A_{12}A_{26}}{A_{22}} \right] \quad C(s) = 4 \left[A_{66} - \frac{(A_{26})^2}{A_{22}} \right] \quad (8)$$

and the shear flow N_{12} can be written as

$$N_{12} = \frac{\partial \Phi_1}{\partial (2\gamma_{12})} = \frac{1}{2} (B(s)\gamma_{11} + C(s)\gamma_{12}) = \text{constant} \quad (9)$$

The value of the shear flow is constant. This is derived by minimizing the energy functional in Eq. (4). Rearrange Eq. (9) to obtain

$$2\gamma_{12} = b(s)\gamma_{11} + 4c(s)N_{12} \quad (10)$$

where

$$b(s) = -2\frac{B(s)}{C(s)} \quad \text{and} \quad c(s) = \frac{1}{C(s)} \quad (11)$$

The strain displacement can be written as

$$\gamma_{11} = U'_1(x) + \tilde{u}'_1(s, x) \quad (12)$$

$$2\gamma_{12} = \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_1}{\partial s} + U'_2(x)\frac{dy}{ds} + U'_3(x)\frac{dz}{ds} + r_n(s)\varphi'(x) \quad (13)$$

where a prime in Eqs. (12) and (13) denotes differentiation with respect to x . From Eqs. (10) and (13) get

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{u}_1}{\partial s} + U'_2(x)\frac{dy}{ds} + U'_3(x)\frac{dz}{ds} + r_n(s)\varphi'(x) = b\gamma_{11} + 4cN_{12} \quad (14)$$

By expressing \tilde{u}_1 as

$$\tilde{u}_1 = -yU'_2(x) - zU'_3(x) + g(s, x) \quad (15)$$

Equation (14) takes the form

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial s} = -r_n(s)\varphi'(x) + bU'_1(x) - byU''_2(x) - bzU''_3(x) + b\frac{\partial g}{\partial x} + 4cN_{12} \quad (16)$$

The unknown function $g(s, x)$ is determined in the following.

For long shells, $d/L \ll 1$ as given in Eq. (1). Therefore $\partial(\)/\partial x \ll \partial(\)/\partial s$. Consequently $b\partial g/\partial x$ is asymptotically small compared to $\partial g/\partial s$ and hence can be neglected in Eq. (16).

The shear flow N_{12} is determined from the condition that $g(s, x)$ should be a single valued continuous function, i.e.

$$\overline{\left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial s}\right)} = \frac{1}{l} \oint \frac{\partial g}{\partial s} ds = 0 \quad (17)$$

The integral in Eq. (17) is performed along the cross-sectional mid-plane closed contour Γ whose length is denoted by l . The bar in Eq. (17) denotes averaging along the closed contour Γ .

Substitute Eq. (16) into Eq. (17) to get

$$N_{12} = \frac{1}{\oint b ds} \left\{ 2A_e\varphi'(x) - \oint b [U'_1(x) - yU''_2(x) - zU''_3(x)] \right\} ds \quad (18)$$

where A_e is the enclosed area of the cross section given by

$$A_e = \frac{1}{2} \oint r_n(s) ds \quad (19)$$

Integrate Eq. (16) and use Eq. (18) to obtain

$$g(s, x) = G(s)\varphi'(x) + g_1(s)U'_1(x) + g_2(s)U''_2(x) + g_3(s)U''_3(x) \quad (20)$$

and the axial displacement takes the form

$$v_1 = U_1(x) - y(s)U_2'(x) - z(s)U_3'(x) + G(s)\varphi'(x) + g_1(s)U_1'(x) + g_2(s)U_2''(x) + g_3(s)U_3''(x) \quad (21)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} G(s) &= \int_0^s \left[\frac{2A_e}{l\bar{c}} c(\tau) - r_n(\tau) \right] d\tau \\ g_1(s) &= \int_0^s \left[b(\tau) - \frac{\bar{b}}{c} c(\tau) \right] d\tau \\ g_2(s) &= - \int_0^s \left[b(\tau)y(\tau) - \frac{\bar{b}y}{c} c(\tau) \right] d\tau \sim O(d^2) \\ g_3(s) &= - \int_0^s \left[b(\tau)z(\tau) - \frac{\bar{b}z}{c} c(\tau) \right] d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The first four terms in Eq. (21) correspond to the classical theory of extension, bending and torsion of beams. In addition to the classical torsional related warping $G(s)\varphi'$, axial strain $g_1(s)U_1'$ and bending related contribution $g_2(s)U_2''$ and $g_3(s)U_3''$ emerge. They are strongly influenced by the material anisotropy, and vanish for materials that are isotropic, orthotropic or whose properties are antisymmetric relative to the shell middle surface. For these layups the coupling parameter $b(s)$ defined in Eq. (11) vanishes. It is worth noting that the expression for torsional related warping $G(s)$ differs from the work of Refs. [13] and [14]-[16].

The displacement field is now completely defined. The expression for the axial component v_1 is provided in Eq. (21) while v_2 and v_3 are given in Eq. (2). Combining Eqs. (15) and (20) with Eqs. (12) and (13), the strain components can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{11} &= U_1'(x) - yU_2''(x) - zU_3''(x) + \frac{\partial g(x, s)}{\partial x} \\ 2\gamma_{12} &= \frac{2A_e}{l\bar{c}} c(s)\varphi' + \left[b(s) - \frac{\bar{b}}{c} c(s) \right] U_1' \left[b(s)y(s) - \frac{\bar{b}y}{c} c(s) \right] U_2'' \left[b(s)z(s) - \frac{\bar{b}z}{c} c(s) \right] U_3'' \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Force-Deformation Relationships

Substitute Eqs. (23) into Eq. (7), and use Eq. (4), while neglecting $\partial g/\partial x$, to get the following expression for the energy of the shell

$$I = \int_0^L \Phi_2 dx \quad (24)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_2 &= \frac{1}{2} \left[C_{11}(U_1')^2 + C_{22}(\varphi')^2 + C_{33}(U_3'')^2 + C_{44}(U_2'')^2 \right] + C_{12}U_1'\varphi' + C_{13}U_1'U_3'' + C_{14}U_1'U_2'' \\ &\quad + C_{23}\varphi'U_3'' + C_{24}\varphi'U_2'' + C_{34}U_2''U_3'' \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The stiffness coefficients C_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 4$) are expressed in terms of the cross section geometry and materials properties by

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11} &= \oint \left(A - \frac{B^2}{C} \right) ds + \frac{[\oint (B/C) ds]^2}{\oint (1/C) ds} \\ C_{12} &= \frac{\oint (B/C) ds}{\oint (1/C) ds} A_e \\ C_{13} &= - \oint \left(A - \frac{B^2}{C} \right) z ds - \frac{\oint (B/C) ds \oint (B/C) z ds}{\oint (1/C) ds} \end{aligned}$$

Table 1: Extension-Torsion Stiffness Coefficients

$$C_{11} = 6.7 \text{ MN} \quad C_{22} = 25.02 \text{ KNm}^2 \quad C_{12} = 124.02 \text{ KNm}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_{14} &= - \oint \left(A - \frac{B^2}{C} \right) y ds - \frac{\oint (B/C) ds \quad \oint (B/C) y ds}{\oint (1/C) ds} \\
 C_{22} &= \frac{1}{\oint (1/C) ds} A_e^2 \\
 C_{23} &= - \frac{\oint (B/C) z ds}{\oint (1/C) ds} A_e \\
 C_{24} &= - \frac{\oint (B/C) y ds}{\oint (1/C) ds} A_e \\
 C_{33} &= \oint \left(A - \frac{B^2}{C} \right) z^2 ds + \frac{[\oint (B/C) z ds]^2}{\oint (1/C) ds} \\
 C_{34} &= \oint \left(A - \frac{B^2}{C} \right) y z ds + \frac{\oint (B/C) y ds \quad \oint (B/C) z ds}{\oint (1/C) ds} \\
 C_{44} &= \oint \left(A - \frac{B^2}{C} \right) y^2 ds + \frac{[\oint (B/C) y ds]^2}{\oint (1/C) ds}
 \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

Parameters A , B and C are defined in terms of the axial stiffness coefficients A_{ij} in Eq. (8).

APPLICATIONS

Consider a thin-walled circular cross section of 101.6 mm diameter made out of a laminate having a $[40/-50/40/-50_2/40]$ stacking sequence. The ply thickness is 0.1397 mm (total thickness = 0.8382 mm) and the material elastic constants are $E_{11} = 147 \text{ GPa}$, $E_{22} = 10.89 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{12} = 6.41 \text{ GPa}$ and $\nu_{12} = 0.38$. The wall stiffness and thickness are uniform along the cross section circumference, i.e. b and c are constant. Therefore, the out-of-plane warping due to axial strain $g_1(s)U'_1(x)$ in Eqs. (21) and (22) vanishes. Moreover, the torsional warping function in Eq. (22) reduces to

$$G(s) = 2A_e \frac{s}{l} - \int_0^s r_n(\tau) d\tau \tag{27}$$

and coincides with the torsional warping function of Ref. [13]. The extension-torsional response of this special cross section is identical to the prediction based on Ref. [13]. The extension (C_{11}), torsion (C_{22}) and extension-torsion coupling (C_{12}) stiffness coefficients are given in Table 1.

The present theory is used to predict the bending response in a laminated composite cantilevered box beam. Figure 2 shows the bending slope variation along the beam span for a $[15]_6$ cantilever made of graphite/epoxy subjected to a 4.448 N (1 lb) transverse tip load. The experimental results are reported in Refs. [14], [16], and [17]. The analytical predictions reported in Refs. [14], [16], and [17] together with results obtained on the basis of the analyses in Ref. [13], [15], [18] and the present theory are combined in Fig. 2. Results show that the present theory is in good agreement with the test data and the closest when compared to the other analytical approaches which include shear deformation (Refs. [13], [14], and [16]), and shear deformation corrections (Refs. [15] and [18]).

CONCLUSION

An asymptotical analysis is used to derive the displacement field and associated stiffness coefficients in thin-walled composite beams. In addition to the classical torsional related warping,

Figure 2: Bending Slope of an Anti-Symmetric $[15]_6$ Cantilever Under 4.448 N (1 lb) Transverse Tip Load

Table 2: Cantilever Geometry and Properties

Width = 24.2 mm	$E_{11} = 0.142$ TPa, $E_{22} = E_{33} = 9.8$ GPa
Depth = 13.46 mm	$G_{12} = G_{13} = 6.0$ GPa, $G_{23} = 4.83$ GPa
Ply thickness = 0.127 mm	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.42$, $\nu_{23} = 0.5$

the out-of-plane warping is shown to be proportional to the axial strain and bending curvature as well. The functions associated with each physical behavior is obtained in closed form. The warping due to axial strain and bending vanish for isotropic and orthotropic materials. Predictions of the present theory are in excellent agreement with test data.

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